

ASSESS THE LEVEL OF PRACTICE ON POSTNATAL CARE AMONG MOTHERS

Mrs. Bananee Dash¹, Dr. Darshan Sohi², Dr. Manjubala Dash³

ABSTRACT:

Introduction: Motherhood is a beautiful experience where by the mother safely delivers a child. it is the magic of creation. care must be given to ensure safe child birth. the mother has a right to get proper medical care and treatment. labor is a natural process, which all pregnant women have to undergo. The postnatal period or puerperium is a period of adjustment after pregnancy when the anatomic and physiologic changes of pregnancy are reversed and body returns to the normal state. This period starts as soon as the placenta is expelled and extends up to the period of 6 weeks. The requirement during this period is nutritious diet, personal hygiene, postnatal exercise, breast feeding, family and immunization to the baby. **Objective:** To assess the level of practice of the mothers regarding postnatal care. **Methodology:** The research approach was quantitative and design was descriptive design. Total 35 mothers were selected with purposive sampling technique. **Result:** The result shows that with regards to distribution of age of primi mother 3 (8.57%) are coming under 22-23 years, Regarding the education of mothers out of 35, 6 (17.15%) have education up to secondary level. The mean practical level of mothers regarding postnatal care. was 17.7 with standard deviation of 1.1 regarding postnatal care. **Conclusion:** Postnatal mothers had fair practices in various aspects of postnatal care. Hence there must be various programmer to create awareness among these mothers.

Keywords: Practice, Postnatal care, mothers, level of practice.

Cite this Article: Bananee Dash, Darshan Sohi, & Manjubala Dash. (2024). Assess the level of practice on postnatal care among mothers. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Health Science*, 1(2), 35–38.

INTRODUCTION:

Parenting is “one process with two components”. The first is practical and mechanical in nature and include cognitive and affective skills of parenting which include and attitude of tenderness, awareness and concerns for the child's needs and desires. The first component in the process of parenting which include care activities such as feeding, clothing, holding, cleaning the infant, protecting it from harm and providing mobility for it. The task-oriented activities or cognitive motor skills are not automatically supplied at the birth of ones child. The parents abilities in these respects have been influenced by cultural and personal experiences (Mattson and Lee, 1992). The postnatal period or puerperium is a period of adjustment after pregnancy when the anatomic and physiologic changes of pregnancy are reversed and body returns to the normal state. This period starts as soon as the placenta is expelled and extends up to the period of 6 weeks. The requirement during this period are nutritious diet, personal hygiene, postnatal exercise, breast feeding, family and immunization to the baby (Helen Varney, 1987). The postnatal mothers have been confined to bed for a long period of time and was unaware about the exercises. They were not able to know about the important of colostrums and few postnatal mother did not feed colostrums.

OBJECTIVE

- To assess the level of practice of the mothers regarding postnatal care
- To associate the level of knowledge with selected variables

METHODOLOGY

The research approach was quantitative and design was descriptive design. Total 35 mothers were selected with purposive sampling technique, those who had normal vaginal delivery and willing to participate in the study were interviewed with the checklist . The study was conducted in the selected village of Odisha [13-15].

RESULT AND FINDINGS: The result shows that with regards to distribution of age of primi mother 3 (8.57%) are coming under 22-23 years, 27 (77.15%) coming under 24-25 years and remaining 5 (14.28%) coming under 26-27 years. Regarding the education of mothers out of 35, 6 (17.15%) have education up to secondary level, 15(42.85%) have education up to higher secondary level, 12 (34.28%) have education up to graduate and the remaining 2 (5.72%) are post graduate. With regard to employment 5 mothers (14.27%) are working as teachers and mill workers, where the remaining 30 (85.73%) are unemployed. Regarding monthly family income 9 (25.72%) had an income below ₹. 4000 per month, 15 (42.85%) earns between ₹. 4001 - ₹. 7000 and 11(31.43%) earns more than ₹. 7000 per month. Regarding religion all the primi mothers 35 (100%) belong to Hindu religion. Regarding the type of family 17 mothers (48.57%) lives in rural area and the rest 18 (51.43%) lives in urban area. Regarding the area of living 25 mothers (71.43%) lives in nuclear family and the rest 10 (28.57%) lives in joint family.

Regarding postnatal care 22 (62.85%) mothers obtained information from relatives and friends, 8 (22.85 %) from neighbours and remaining 5 (14.28%) from health personnels (Tab-1)

Tab-1- Distribution of demographic variable of the Postnatal mothers.

S. No.	Demographic Variables	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
1.	Age	3	8.57
	a) 22-23 years	27	77.15
	b) 24-25 years	5	14.28
	c) 26-27 years		
2.	Educational status		
	a) Secondary	6	17.15
	b) Higher Secondary	15	42.85
	c) Graduate	12	34.28
d) Post graduate	2	5.72	
3.	Occupation of mother		
	a) Employed	5	14.27
b) Unemployed	30	85.73	
4.	Monthly family income		
	a) Below ₹. 4000	9	25.72
	b) ₹. 4001 - ₹. 7000	15	42.85
c) ₹. 7000 and above	11	31.43	
5.	Religion		
	a) Hindu	35	100
	b) Muslim	0	0
c) Christian	0	0	
6.	Type of Family		
	a) Nuclear family	17	48.57
b) Joint family	18	51.43	
7.	Area of living		
	a) Rural	25	71.43
b) Urban	10	28.57	

8.	Sources of information regarding postnatal care		
	a) Relatives and friends	22	62.85
	b) Neighbours	8	22.85
	c) Health personnels	5	14.30

Table (2) shows the mean practical level of mothers regarding postnatal care. Result showed that mothers mean practice level was 17.7 with standard deviation of 1.1 regarding postnatal care.

Tab2- Distribution of level of Practice among Postnatal Mothers

Variable	Mean	S.D
Practice	17.7	1.1

Conclusion- Postnatal mothers had fair practices in various aspects of postnatal care. Hence there must be various programmes to create awareness among these mothers.

REFERENCE:

1. Adcle Pillitteri (1999), "Maternal and child health nursing" (3 edi) Uppincott, U.S.
2. A.M. Virkud, (1995), "Maual of Practical Obsterics and Neotalogy", Ist edition, D.K. Publications.
3. Amarnath G. Bhide et.a; (2000), "A text book of obstetrics for Nurses and midwives" (ed), Jaypee brothers, Delhi, Stuart Campbell et.al, (2000)," Obstetrics by ten teachers," (17th ed), Astrazzenca, London.
4. Babak et. al, "Maternity and women's health care", 6th ed, Mosby, (1997)
5. Basaranthappa B.T. (2003), "Nursing Research", 25th edition, Jaypee brothers, New Delhi.
6. Bennet V. Ruth Myles, et.al, (1998), "Text Book For Midwives", 13th edition, Edinburgh Company, London.
7. Hendon (1998) "American Journal of Nursing", John wiley and sons Publications New York.
8. "The Journal of Family Welfare", JIMA Publications Vol – II 1999.
9. "The Indian Journal of Nursing and Midwives", May 1998.
10. Cartis stone et.al, "The American Journal of Obstetric and Gynaecology", Publish out 1998.
11. Women and child care, "The Couple Family Health Magazine", November 2001.
12. "Family Planning Method – Health Action", Publication 1999.
13. Avery,Burket(1992),"Postnatal Care", Journal of Nurse and Midwifery 39 (2)
14. Pathfinder International (1997) "Comprehensive Reproductive Health", and Family Planning Training Curriculum: Module – 8 Lactational Amenorrhea and Breastfeeding Support.